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Towards Understanding “Afolaranmi’s Five ‘W’ Questions” in a Research Scope

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Abstract

Every research should have a scope that will guide the researcher in their study. This concise guide article presents some components of a research scope. This is done by using “Afolaranmi’s Five ‘W’ Questions” (that is, what, who, where, why, and when) to explain these components. The five “W” questions deal with key concepts or variables in the research; people or (sample drawn from the) population of the study; location of the study; rationale behind the study; and time frame of the study. Using) research design and based on a suggested working title and aim of a study, these questions are explained with samples for answers to each question. An image was also provided to illustrate these principles graphically. A sample of a full scope was also provided to demonstrate the principles. It was concluded that using these “W” questions would help researchers to grasp the full essence of their study. Therefore, every researcher should clearly define and state their scope by answering the “Afolaranmi’s Five ‘W’ Questions” presented in the article.

Keywords: Scope, Delimitation, Research, Concepts, Variables, Population, Time Frame

Introduction

There is a driving force apart from the aim of research that every researcher must clearly define and articulate if the researcher would achieve the desired aim of the study. This is called the scope of the study. While some scholars and/or institutions would combine the scope with delimitation and/or limitation, this author prefers to distinguish only the scope in this article. The delimitation of the study refers to the “potential weaknesses that are usually out of the researcher’s control, and are closely associated with the chosen research design, statistical model constraints, funding constraints, or other factors” (Theofanidis & Fountouki, 2019:156). These are what the researcher deliberately leaves out of their study. On the other hand, limitations are “constraints that are largely beyond [researcher’s] control but could affect the study outcome” (Simon & Goes, 2013). However, the scope of the study is specifically the extent or range of the research including the key concepts or variable, population and context or location of the research. Therefore, that aim of this article is to give some components in a scope of a research through “Afolaranmi’s Five ‘W’ Questions”. A descriptive research design will be used based on a working title and aim of a perceived study to explain these questions with samples for answers to each question.

The “W” Questions in a Research Scope

Akanle, Ademuson and Shittu (2020:105) identified what the authors termed “4Ws2Hs”, that is, “(1) what to study (2) why it must be studied (3) when it must be studied (4) why what is not (to be) studied (5) how much and (6). how it must be studied” in a scope of a study. However, in his attempt to present how to write thesis in a university, this author presented five "W" questions to address in the scope of a research (Afolaranmi, 2025:25). The author presented “Afolaranmi’s Five ‘W’ Questions” in a figure as reproduced in Figure 1.

Afolaranmi's Five "W" Questions of Research Scope

Figure 1: Afolaranmi's Five "W" Questions of Research Scope (Afolaranmi, 2025:46)

These five "W" questions will be addressed one after the other. The author adapted his PhD thesis title and scope to illustrate the explanation for each question. The thesis title is "Use of Social Media for Sustainable Peace by Church Pastors of the Nigerian Baptist Convention, 2010-2020" (Afolaranmi, 2022). However, for this paper, the adapted and suggested title that is used for illustrations is "Use of Social Media for Sustainable Peace by Pastors in Ibadan Metropolis, 2010-2020." The suggested aim is to examine how Baptist pastors in the Ibadan metropolis use social media in mediative dialogue to Baptist resolve conflicts in building peace among the congregation.

1. *The “W” Question One: What Specifically Are You Researching?*

This has to do with the key concepts or variables that the study is focusing on. A concept is an abstract idea or a mental construct that represents a phenomenon or a characteristic. On the other hand, a variable is a measurable representation of a concept, allowing researchers to quantify or categorize the phenomenon (Bhattacharjee, 2012). The variables or main concepts in the suggested title are social media, sustainable peace (specifically, using mediative dialogue as a means of conflict resolution), and Baptist pastors.

2. *The “W” Question Two: Who Are Directly Involved in Your Study?*

This is typically the research population. A research population is “comprised of the individuals, dyads, groups, organizations, or other entities one seeks to understand and to whom or to which the study results may be generalized or transferred and is the principal group about which the research is concerned” (Casteel & Bridier, 2021: 343). The population of the suggested title consists of all Baptist pastors in the Ibadan metropolis.

3. *The “W” Question Three: Where Are You Conducting This Research?*

This is the context of the research. A study cannot be carried out in a vacuum. It cannot be done generally. It must have or be linked to a particular geographical location. This is fundamental in research as it “provides the essential context within which data is collected, analyzed, and interpreted” (Farmer, 2025). For the suggested title, Ibadan metropolis is the specific location of the study.

4. *The “W” Question Four: Why Are You Particular About this Study?*

This explains why a researcher is focusing on the main concepts or variables in the study. It also explains why the researcher is focusing on the chosen population and location of the study. Rationales for the suggested title are: (i) technological tools are playing significant roles in this digital world, and the emergence of social media has tremendously changed the ways people communicate throughout the world; (ii) pastors have been called into the ministry of reconciliation. Ibadan metropolis was chosen because there are substantial numbers of Baptist pastors in the metropolis compared

relatively to other areas in Nigeria; and (iii) Ibadan metropolis is part of a state conference known as the Ibadan Baptist Conference, which is one of the largest conferences in the Nigerian Baptist Convention.

5. The “W” Question Five: When or What Time Frame Does the Research Cover?

This is not the timeline of your research! It is the time frame of the study. Timeline has to do with current and future period when you want to do what in the process of carrying out the research. Time frame has to do with the past period that you are focusing on in the study. It is expected that you cannot study the current day, week, month or year. So, the time frame must be some time in the past. For the suggested title, the time frame for the research was between 2010 and 2020.

An Example of a Research Scope

Having explained “Afolaranmi’s Five ‘W’ Questions” with specific illustrations, here is an example of a scope for a study as adapted from a PhD thesis (Afolaranmi, 2022):

The study focuses on using social media in mediative dialogue as a means of conflict resolution among Baptist pastors of churches in Ibadan metropolis. Technological tools are playing significant roles in this digital world, and the emergence of social media has tremendously changed the ways people communicate throughout the world. Pastors have been called into the ministry of reconciliation. Ibadan metropolis was chosen because there are substantial numbers of Baptist pastors in the metropolis compared relatively to other areas in Nigeria. Besides, the Ibadan metropolis is part of a state conference known as the Ibadan Baptist Conference, which is one of the largest conferences in the Nigerian Baptist Convention. Since there are many categories of social media, only Facebook and Twitter as social network services (SNS) and WhatsApp and Telegram as instant messaging apps are focused on in the study. This focuses on how peaceful and non-violent societies as one of the blueprints of the Sustainable Development Goals of the

United Nations can be achieved. The time frame for this research is between 2010 and 2020.

Conclusion

A well-defined scope of a study is fundamental to the success of the study. It helps to focus on the study and ensure that it is on track. Therefore, every researcher should clearly define and state their scope by meticulously answering the “Afolaranmi’s Five ‘W’ Questions” presented in this article.

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